

Relationship Between Urobilinogen and Singing

Fatima Idrees*, Syed Bilal Hussain, Muhammad Imran Qadir & Tayyaba Yousaf

Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.
Corresponding Author (Fatima Idrees) - idreeschaudhary2222@gmail.com*

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ABSTRACT

Singing may cause urobilinogen in a person by releasing some sort of chemicals from brain. The standard average of students that took part in this experiment was 90 students. They were from Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan. They were mostly of age 18 to 22. The aim of this study was to find whether there is any tie-up between singing and urobilinogen level. The student's opinions were noted after examining their urobilinogen level. We found out that most of the students have 0.1 mg/dL urobilinogen in their urine which is normal.

Keywords: Singing; Urobilinogen; Urine; Chemicals; Age; Brain.

Introduction

Urobilinogen is uncolored and is the end product of the bilirubin reduction. Bacterial activity on bilirubin results in the creation of urobilinogen in intestine. It is transformed into a yellow pigment substance called urobilin which is visible in urine. While in the intestine it is converted into a brown substance called stercobilin. Most of the urobilinogen manufactured is redistributed by the liver and then goes back to the intestines [1-2]. During the circulation, a small amount of it can also reach the kidneys and form urinary urobilinogen. Various diseases like liver dysfunction or hemolytic diseases can occur because of the greater amount of urobilinogen in urine. Normal urine contains about 1 mg/dL of urobilinogen [3-4]. An increase in this number can result in the risk and should be checked. Increase in the use of drugs or congenital enzymatic jaundice can cause urobilinogen level in the urine to decrease. On the other hand, hemolytic anaemia, minimizing liver function and hepatic infection can result in its level to accelerate. Iron supplements or liver transplant can be recommended for its treatment.

Singing is considered to be a remedy of all sorts of problems like emotional, physical and even spiritual. Singing not only helps in better sleep but also better body posture. It can also help to strengthen the immune system and relieve muscle rigidity. Besides it, it can also cure sadness and frustration. It can alleviate a person's mood and confidences. So that singing may cause urobilinogen in a person by releasing some sort of chemicals from brain.

The aim of this current study was to tie up the link between singing and urobilinogen.

Materials and Methods

All types of urinalysis tests do not require any special equipment. The only things that can be used are containers for collecting urine and some sterilizer to clean hands before starting. The precautions are also very basic which are the same before starting every medical test. The patient is asked to mentally relax before the test.

Urobilinogen Measurement

By using urobilinogen test dip-sticks, the level of urobilinogen can be checked. These sticks employ P-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde that can react under acidic environment with urobilinogen. It can result in

creating pink pigment. We use this dip- stick method in our experiment. Their pink color visibility indicated the standard level of urobilinogen in urine. The cure however varies according to the amount of urobilinogen diagnosed.

Study Design

This project was designed in such a way that all the students first had to test their urine to determine urobilinogen level. After that, they were requested to fill the opinion form by answering their likeness on singing. All the 90 students had to follow these rules strictly. For proper calculations MS excel can be used. MS word can be used to write all the analysis found.

Statistical Analysis

For analysis purpose, Statistix software can be commonly used due to its fast response.

Results and Discussions

Gender	Likeness in Singing		Dis-likeness in Singing	
	Urobilinogen Present	Urobilinogen Absent	Urobilinogen Present	Urobilinogen Absent
Male	8	3	7	1
Female	37	9	22	3

As we can see from the table that most of the students have urobilinogen in urine. The average of males who liked singing and have urobilinogen was 72.72%. while aggregate of females who liked singing and had urobilinogen was 80.4%. Talking about singing dis likeness, the percentage of presence of urobilinogen in male was 87.5% and female was 88 percent. Mesobilirubinogen and the term urobilinogen both considered to be same. There may be some relation between them. Cartoon watching has there some relation between urobilinogen. There are different analytical methods for measuring bilirubin level within, urine, and serum. Numerous problems and metabolic illness are connected to variation with concentration of bilirubin by the normal amount within serum. Questionnaire studies are important in finding out results and illustrating the data and helpful in analysis.

Conclusion

This experiment indicates no as such link between singing and urobilinogen. Having up to 1 mg/dL level of urobilinogen in urine is absolutely normal. Its higher level can result in hepatitis, Cirrhosis and liver damage. Sometimes quitting the medicine or drugs that you are taking can also help to bring urobilinogen level back to normal.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This study did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this study.

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